

Study of Pulmonary Function Tests in Healthy School Children of 6 -12 Years of Age in Howrah District of West Bengal in Eastern IndiaSubhamitra Maulik¹, Ranabir Mazumdar², Krishna Laskar³, Nazir Abdul Wasim⁴¹Assistant Professor, Dept of Physiology, Medical College, Kolkata²Assistant Professor, Dept of Ophthalmology, Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay Govt Medical College and Hospital, Uluberia, Howrah³Assistant Professor, Dept of Physiology, Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay Govt Medical College and Hospital, Uluberia, Howrah⁴Associate Professor, Dept of Pathology, Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay Govt Medical College and Hospital, Uluberia, Howrah

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Pulmonary function tests (PFT) have become an integral part of assessment of pulmonary diseases. In clinical practice, spirometry, physiological test that measures volume or flow is equated with pulmonary function tests in day to day practice. Standard reference values are essential for meaningful interpretation of these tests. Pulmonary function values are influenced by age, sex, height, weight, body surface area, race and geographical location. Children belonging to the age group 6 – 12 years fall in the category of vulnerable population suffering from cardio respiratory illness in our country. Due to paucity of predictive normal values of PFT in these children, these tests are not routinely performed in our country, but they are necessary for overall assessment and management of respiratory diseases.

Keywords: PFT, FVC, FEV₁, FEV₁

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Introduction

As far as our research is concerned, no regional reference standards for pulmonary function for children belonging to the age group 6 – 12 years has been established in Eastern India, especially in West Bengal. So the present study was conducted to obtain standard reference values of pulmonary function tests in normal school children belonging to the 6 – 12 years of age group in Howrah District of West Bengal in Eastern India. Prediction equations were also derived.

Aims and Objectives

To obtain reference values of FVC, FEV₁, FEV₁%, FEV_{25-75%} and PEF among normal children aged 6-12 yrs in West Bengal in Eastern India.

To show any relationship of lung function values with Age, Weight, Height, Sex, Body Mass Index and to derive prediction equations for pulmonary function tests.

Materials and Methods

It's a Cross-sectional observational study. A total of 310 (138 boys + 172 girls) school children were taken belonging to the age category of 6-12 yrs and are normal, healthy, cooperative, non-smoker, physically and mentally fit, with a time plan of 2013

to 2014. The schools were situated in Bally and Bally west circle in Howrah District of West Bengal, from different primary schools to obtain a representative cross section of this region. Boys and girls in each category (6-7 yrs, 7-8 yrs, 8-9 yrs, 9-10 yrs, 10-11 yrs, 11-12 yrs) were included. Informed consent was taken from the parents and the respective school authorities before enrolment. Children whose guardians have objected to the procedures and those having Febrile illness, Upper respiratory infections in past 2 weeks, or having Acute or chronic respiratory diseases or any major systemic disease like Cardiac or Renal problems, Clinically significant Anemia, Drug intake which has effect on PFT, Allergy, Children with bony deformity of chest or spine, Any Muscular weakness, Family history of Atopy, Asthma or other chronic lung disease. Smokers – Both active and passive. Subjects who will not be able to give desired cooperation.

Regulatory Clearances Required

- Permission has been taken from the chairman, District Primary school council, Howrah, Government of West Bengal, to study the PFTS in

the children of the schools under his jurisdiction. (Copy Enclosed).

- Permission has also been granted from the IPGMER Research Oversight Committee (Institutional Ethics Committee). (Copy Enclosed).

Safety issues and degree of risk involved

So far this study was concerned there was no risk to any subject, as we also know that the procedures was simple, rapid and non-invasive.

Research Execution

1. Study area

- Government Primary schools in Bally circle and Bally West Circle in the district of Howrah in West Bengal.
- Institute of Post Graduate Medical Education & Research-the physiology department, Kolkata.

2. Study tools

- i. For physical and clinical examination

Weighing scale

Stethoscope

Measuring tape

Sphygmo manometer

Torch, hammer, cotton etc

Nose clip

- ii. For PFT- windows based Digital Spirometer "SpiroWin" (Genesis Medical System Private Limited)

3. Precise and Detailed Methodology

- i. Proper informed consent was taken from the participating subjects.
- ii. Prior permission of school authorities was taken and written consent from the parents or guardian of the students involved in the study was obtained.
- iii. Study was conducted among boys and girls in the age group of 6-12 yrs in the primary schools of Bally west circle of Howrah district.
- iv. Detailed history was taken as per case record format.
- v. Detailed physical examination in the general and systemic category.
- vi. Subject Demographics & related information was noted which included anthropometric measurements like Age, Weight, Height, Sex, body Surface Area, body Mass Index, race, socioeconomic status.
- vii. All the measurements were performed in class rooms provided by the schools between 12 noon and 2 pm to keep diurnal variation to the

minimum and also as per convenience of school authorities and students.

With appropriate coaching the young children of 6-12 years age group were able to perform spirometry that is acceptable for analysis. A bright pleasant atmosphere with age appropriate toys, sweets ,reading material and art were very important to make them at ease. Encouragement, detailed but simple instructions throughout the test, lack of intimidation and visual feedback during the manoeuvre helped in performing the test successfully. Even if they were unsuccessful at the first session, they learned to be less intimidated and performed better at the subsequent sessions[18-19].

4. Details of Technique of PFT

- a. Children were tested in sitting and erect position with head straight ; in a chair with handle and without any wheels to prevent from falling. There should not be any tight clothing around neck and body during the performance.
- b. Before testing, procedure was explained and demonstrated to each child until familiarity was achieved.
- c. A new disposable mouthpiece was used every time for a new candidate. The mouthpiece was put inside the mouth with lips closed properly around it avoiding licks.
- d. To start with subject was allowed to take a few tidal breaths to get accustomed to the equipment.
- e. Each child was asked to take a deep breath and blow into the mouth piece as hard and fast as he/she can.
- f. Nose clips or manual occlusion of nose were used during the manoeuvre.
- g. At least three trials were given & best of three was chosen for analysis.
- h. The same spirometer was used throughout the study and all the tests were performed by me Dr. Subhamitra Maulik.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was carried out using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) 16.0 and analysis was carried out separately in boys and girls.

Parameters of Evaluation

- i. Age
- ii. sex
- iii. Weight
- iv. Height
- v. BMI
- vi. PFT values
 - a. Forced Vital Capacity (FVC)
 - b. Timed Vital Capacity 1 second (FEV₁)
 - c. FEV₁/FVC ratio
 - d. Forced Expiratory Flow 25-75% (FEF_{25-75%})
 - e. Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR)

Result and Analysis

Table 1: Age distribution of the children

Age (in years)(n=310)	Boys (n=148)	Girls (n=172)
6	2 (25%)	6 (75%)
7	14 (48.3%)	15 (51.7%)
8	34 (60.7%)	22 (39.3%)
9	24 (34.3%)	46 (65.7%)
10	38 (54.3%)	32 (45.7%)
11	22 (41.5%)	31 (58.5%)
12	4 (16.7%)	20 (83.3%)

The number of boys and girls belonging to each age group and their relative percentages shows that the number of boys are less than the girls in the extremes of the age groups.

Table 2: Pulmonary function test values of girls in relation to age

Age (years)	Number (n)	FVC (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC (\pm SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (\pm SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR (\pm SD) (litre/sec)
6	6	0.452 (\pm 0.214)	0.439 (\pm 0.216)	9.49 (\pm 4.071)	1.22 (\pm 0.008)	0.703 (\pm 0.356)
7	15	1.018 (\pm 0.604)	0.821 (\pm 0.473)	8.09 (\pm 7.183)	1.118 (\pm 0.806)	1.587 (\pm 0.838)
8	22	0.921 (\pm 0.245)	0.809 (\pm 0.222)	8.812 (\pm 7.86)	1.123 (\pm 0.319)	1.534 (\pm 0.463)
9	46	1.189 (\pm 0.320)	0.985 (\pm 0.278)	8.294 (\pm 8.508)	1.083 (\pm 0.465)	1.651 (\pm 0.645)
10	32	1.188 (\pm 0.287)	1.006 (\pm 0.267)	8.423 (\pm 10.753)	1.204 (\pm 0.447)	1.596 (\pm 0.606)
11	31	1.328 (\pm 0.39)	1.146 (\pm 0.426)	8.454 (\pm 8.697)	1.491 (\pm 0.555)	1.877 (\pm 0.860)
12	20	1.4095 (\pm 0.347)	1.161 (\pm 0.352)	8.15 (\pm 0.865)	1.73 (\pm 0.55)	2.12 (\pm 0.77)

The lung function parameters in girls shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with age especially in FVC & FEV₁. But in FEF_{25-75%} the age category of 7 & 9 years showed a slight decrease then their preceding categories. Similarly in PEFR the group of 8 & 10 years showed a slight decrease than the rest which showed an increase in the parameters with age

Table 3: Pulmonary function test values of boys in relation to age

Age (years)	Number (n)	FVC (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC(\pm SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (\pm SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR (\pm SD) (litre/sec)
6	2	0.758 (\pm 0.3076)	0.579 (\pm 0.244)	7.6 (\pm 1.43)	0.96 (\pm 0.38)	1.105 (\pm 0.062)
7	14	1.019 (\pm 0.307)	0.834 (\pm 0.225)	8.262 (\pm 8.103)	0.984 (\pm 0.493)	1.726 (\pm 0.715)
8	34	1.188 (\pm 0.22)	0.99 (\pm 0.202)	8.334 (\pm 8.93)	1.138 (\pm 0.38)	1.833 (\pm 0.592)
9	24	1.282 (\pm 0.26)	1.066 (\pm 0.25)	8.285 (\pm 8.294)	1.274 (\pm 0.55)	2.013 (\pm 0.82)
10	38	1.39 (\pm 0.269)	1.1994 (\pm 0.26)	8.593 (\pm 10.164)	1.54 (\pm 0.42)	2.02 (\pm 0.685)
11	22	1.27 (\pm 0.483)	1.09 (\pm 0.43)	8.45 (\pm 9.69)	1.43 (\pm 0.4885)	1.924 (\pm 0.7153)
12	4	1.41 (\pm 0.52)	1.182 (\pm 0.472)	8.38 (\pm 11.146)	1.114 (\pm 0.73)	2.55 (\pm 0.86)

The lung function parameters in boys shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with age. Most of the values in the boys are greater than those of girls. But the age category of 11 years showed a slight decrease in the values than their preceding categories.

Table 4: Pulmonary function test values of girls in relation to weight

Weight (kg)	Number (n)	FVC (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC (\pm SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (\pm SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR (\pm SD) (litre/sec)
15-24	88	0.985 (\pm 0.362)	0.826 (\pm 0.296)	8.442 (\pm 8.553)	1.098 (\pm 0.49)	1.423 (\pm 0.64)
25-34	60	1.27 (\pm 0.32)	1.06 (\pm 0.28)	8.29 (\pm 9.89)	1.26 (\pm 0.44)	1.78 (\pm 0.67)
35-44	19	1.56 (\pm 0.37)	1.38 (\pm 0.43)	8.56 (\pm 9.07)	1.97 (\pm 0.50)	2.44 (\pm 0.79)
45-54	5	1.48 (\pm 0.24)	1.35 (\pm 0.28)	9.07 (\pm 4.99)	1.67 (\pm 0.48)	1.95 (\pm 0.61)

The lung function parameters in girls shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with weight . but girls >45 kg showed a decrease in the values of the parameters.

Table 5: Pulmonary function test values of boys in relation to weight

Weight (kg)	Number (n)	FVC (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC (\pm SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (\pm SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR (\pm SD) (litre/sec)
15-24	92	1.186 (\pm 0.273)	0.987 (\pm 0.254)	8.31 (\pm 8.52)	1.177 (\pm 0.457)	1.852 (\pm 0.693)
25-34	35	1.382 (\pm 0.401)	1.214 (\pm 0.349)	8.776 (\pm 9.88)	1.526 (\pm 0.459)	2.159 (\pm 0.7299)
35-44	9	1.343 (\pm 0.331)	1.133 (\pm 0.36)	8.12 (\pm 9.845)	1.663 (\pm 0.608)	1.912 (\pm 0.675)
45-54	2	1.91 (\pm 0.0071)	1.393 (\pm 0.0042)	7.305 (\pm 0.0707)	1.373 (\pm 0.011)	1.674 (\pm 0.00849)

The lung function parameters in boys shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with weight. Most of the values in the boys are greater than those of girls. But here boys >45 kg showed a slight decrease in the value of FEF_{25-75%} & PEFR. A slight fall of PEFR values are observed in boys >35 kg also.

Table 6: Pulmonary function test values of girls in relation to height

Height (cm)	Number (n)	FVC (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC (\pm SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (\pm SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR (\pm SD) (litre/sec)
105—119	32	0.88 (\pm 0.492)	0.73 (\pm 0.393)	8.36 (\pm 8.37)	1.02 (\pm 0.63)	1.35 (\pm 0.74)
120—134	81	1.08 (\pm 0.27)	0.91 (\pm 0.23)	8.43 (\pm 9.26)	1.135 (\pm 0.399)	1.56 (\pm 0.604)
135—149	54	1.39 (\pm 0.30)	1.18 (\pm 0.31)	8.404 (\pm 9.21)	1.534 (\pm 0.498)	2.004 (\pm 0.741)
150—164	5	1.91 (\pm 0.292)	1.714 (\pm 0.43)	8.849 (\pm 10.14)	2.097 (\pm 0.65)	2.57 (\pm 0.736)

The lung function parameters in girls shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with height .

Table 7: Pulmonary function test values of boys in relation to height

Height (cm)	Number (n)	FVC (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (\pm SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC (\pm SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (\pm SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR (\pm SD) (litre/sec)
105—119	26	0.924 (\pm 0.199)	0.765 (\pm 0.201)	8.223 (\pm 8.78)	0.989 (\pm 0.441)	1.53 (\pm 0.613)
120—134	80	1.289 (\pm 0.22)	1.094 (\pm 0.216)	8.491 (\pm 9.096)	1.322 (\pm 0.481)	2.0385 (\pm 0.693)
135—149	32	1.448 (\pm 0.447)	1.216 (\pm 0.392)	8.312 (\pm 9.75)	1.496 (\pm 0.463)	1.99 (\pm 0.705)

The lung function parameters in boys shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with height . Most of the values in the boys are greater than those of girls. But a slight fall in PEFR value was observed in the category of 135-149 cm.

Table 8: Pulmonary function test values of girls in relation to BMI

BMI	Number (n)	FVC(±SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (±SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC(±SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (±SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR(±SD) (litre/sec)
11--14.99	92	1.05 (±0.29)	0.88 (±0.26)	8.39 (±9.001)	1.11 (±0.432)	1.55 (±0.57)
15—18.99	69	1.29 (±0.49)	1.099 (±0.44)	8.49 (±9.26)	1.42 (±0.602)	1.85 (±0.89)
19—22.99	10	1.304 (±0.295)	1.073 (±0.306)	8.16 (±8.04)	1.53 (±0.57)	1.822 (±0.61)
23—26.99	1	1.57 (±0)	1.514 (±0)	9.663 (±1)	2.38 (±0)	2.897 (±0)

The lung function parameters in girls shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with body mass index . but in the category of 19-22.99, a slight fall of the values of FEV₁ & PEFR were observed.

Table 9: Pulmonary function test values of boys in relation to BMI

BMI	Number (n)	FVC(±SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ (±SD) (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC(±SD)	FEF _{25-75%} (±SD) (litre/sec)	PEFR(±SD) (litre/sec)
11--14.99	88	1.230 (±0.296)	1.033 (±0.273)	8.3715 (±8.2779)	1.189 (±0.464)	1.885 (±0.677)
15—18.99	36	1.268 (±0.398)	1.079 (±0.3654)	8.454 (±10.71)	1.445 (±0.486)	2.015 (±0.801)
19—22.99	10	1.305 (±0.326)	1.145 (±0.3413)	8.526 (±11.744)	1.713 (±0.58)	2.08 (±0.735)
23—26.99	4	1.59 (±0.365)	1.28 (±0.141)	8.1935 (±10.27)	1.392 (±0.023)	1.803 (±0.1485)

The lung function parameters in boys shows that the values are increasing in correspondence with body mass index. Most of the values in the boys are greater than those of girls. But a slight decrease in FEF_{25-75%} & PEFR were observed in the category of 23-26.99.

Table 10: Pearson`s correlation coefficients (r) for pulmonary function test values and anthropometry of girls

Age and Anthropometric Measurements	FVC (litre)	FEV ₁ (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC	FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	PEFR (litre/sec)
Age (years)	r=0.443* p=0.000	r=0.409* p=0.000	r= - 0.130 p=0.089	r=0.326* p=0.000	r=0.317* p=0.000
Weight (kg)	r=0.536* p=0.000	r=0.555* p=0.000	r=0.083 p=0.279	r=0.486* p=0.000	r=0.402* p=0.000
Height (cm)	r=0.590* p=0.000	r=0.590* p=0.000	r=0.025 p=0.744	r=0.442* p=0.000	r=0.405* p=0.000
BMI (Kg/m ²)	r=0.287* p=0.000	r=0.313* p=0.000	r=0.103 p=0.177	r=0.357* p=0.000	r=0.246* p=0.001

*correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

All lung function parameters except FEV₁/FVC showed significant correlation with age , weight , height , and BMI in girls.

Table 11: Pearson`s correlation coefficients (r) for pulmonary function test values and anthropometry of boys

Age and Anthropometric Measurements	FVC (litre)	FEV ₁ (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC	FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	PEFR (litre/sec)
Age (years)	r=0.311* p=0.000	r=0.341* p=0.000	r= 0.116 p=0.175	r=0.307* p=0.000	r=0.179** p=0.036
Weight (kg)	r=0.386* p=0.000	r=0.375* p=0.000	r=0.027 p=0.756	r=0.375* p=0.000	r=0.136 p=0.113
Height (cm)	r=0.507* p=0.000	r=0.497* p=0.000	r=0.050 p=0.562	r=0.367* p=0.000	r=0.222* p=0.009
BMI (Kg/m ²)	r=0.174** p=0.041	r=0.173** p=0.042	r=0.030 p=0.724	r=0.267* p=0.002	r=0.053 p=0.534

*correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

** correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed)

All lung function parameters except FEV₁/FVC showed significant correlation with age, weight, height, and BMI in boys. PEFR did not show good correlation with weight and BMI but the correlation with age and height were significant among the boys.

Table 12: Pulmonary function distribution in boys and girls for the whole sample

Spirometry parameters	Mean ±SD	Median	25 th percentile	50 th percentile	75 th percentile
FVC (litre)	1.2053 ±0.373	1.199	0.961	1.199	1.436
FEV ₁ (litre)	1.0172 ±0.338	1.001	0.798	1.001	1.220
FEV ₁ /FVC	84.111 ±9.108	84.16	76.53	84.16	91.42
FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	1.282 ±0.522	1.224	0.948	1.224	1.559
PEFR (litre/sec)	1.798 ±0.728	1.753	1.317	1.753	2.21

A display of the mean, median and percentile values at the 25th, 50th and the 75th level along with the standard deviations (SD) for the whole cohort of boys and girls.

Table 13: Pulmonary function distribution in boys for the whole sample

Spirometry parameters	Mean ±SD	Median	25 th percentile	50 th percentile	75 th percentile
FVC (litre)	1.256 ±0.3313	1.2905	1.0475	1.2905	1.449
FEV ₁ (litre)	1.0603 ±0.3032	1.067	0.8798	1.067	1.264
FEV ₁ /FVC	83.992 ±9.196	84.61	76.775	84.61	91.485
FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	1.2997 ±0.495	1.2235	0.91	1.2235	1.6285
PEFR (litre/sec)	1.9311 ±0.7043	1.887	1.317	1.887	2.3995

A display of the mean, median and percentile values at the 25th, 50th and the 75th level along with the standard deviations (SD) for the whole cohort of boys.

Table 14: Pulmonary function distribution in girls for the whole sample

Spirometry parameters	Mean ±SD	Median	25 th percentile	50 th percentile	75 th percentile
FVC (litre)	1.165 ±0.40006	1.060	0.961	0.9205	1.393
FEV ₁ (litre)	0.983 ±0.3604	0.960	0.798	0.7503	1.275
FEV ₁ /FVC	84.2067 ±9.063	84.045	76.53	76.35	91.42
FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	1.2675 ±0.5435	1.224	0.948	0.963	1.516
PEFR (litre/sec)	1.691 ±0.732	1.580	1.317	1.240	2.019

A display of the mean, median and percentile values at the 25th, 50th and the 75th level along with the standard deviations (SD) for the whole cohort of girls.

Table 15: Independent sample 't' test of lung function parameters and anthropometric values of boys and girls of the whole cohort

Parameters	Sex	Mean (± SD)	Pvalue*(2tailed)	95% confidence interval of the difference	
				lower	Upper
Age (years)	Female	9.49 (±1.588)	0.155	-0.038	+0.638
	Male	9.19 (±1.391)			
Weight (kg)	Female	25.97 (±7.187)	0.148	-0.789	+2.328
	Male	25.2 (± 6.599)			
Height (cm)	Female	129.51 (±11.24)	.001	-1.682	+2.955
	Male	128.87 (±9.009)			
BMI (Kg/m ²)	Female	1.519 (±2.246)	0.59	-3.7136	+0.7421
	Male	1.501 (±2.746)			
FVC (litre)	Female	1.1646(±0.4001)	0.061	-1.75	-0.008
	Male	1.2561 (±0.331)			
FEV ₁ (litre)	Female	0.983 (±0.360)	0.187	-1.53	-0.002
	Male	1.0603(±0.3032)			
FEV ₁ /FVC	Female	8.421 (±9.063)	0.859	-1.84	+2.27
	Male	8.3992 (±9.196)			
FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	Female	1.267 (±0.544)	0.810	-1.498	+0.0852
	Male	1.2997 (±0.495)			
PEFR (litre/sec)	Female	1.691 (±0.732)	0.290	-4.02	-0.078
	Male	1.931 (±0.290)			

*p < 0.05 to be significant

Independent sample 't' test of lung function parameters and anthropometric values of boys and girls of the whole cohort did not find any statistically significant difference in lung function between both sex groups.

Table 16: Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) for pulmonary function test values and anthropometry of the whole cohort

Age and Anthropometric Measurements	FVC (litre)	FEV ₁ (litre)	FEV ₁ /FVC	FEF _{25-75%} (litre/sec)	PEFR (litre/sec)
Age (years)	r=0.378* p=0.000	r=0.368* p=0.000	r= -0.026 p=0.644	r=0.314* p=0.000	r=0.240* p=0.000
Weight (kg)	r=0.468* p=0.000	r=0.476* p=0.000	r=0.059 p=0.297	r=0.439* p=0.000	r=0.278* p=0.000
Height (cm)	r=0.553* p=0.000	r=0.549* p=0.000	r=0.035 p=0.238	r=0.412* p=0.000	r=0.324* p=0.000
BMI (Kg/m ²)	r=0.226* p=0.000	r=0.240* p=0.000	r=0.067 p=0.541	r=0.310* p=0.000	r=0.143 p=0.012

*correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

All lung function parameters except FEV₁/FVC showed significant correlation with age, weight, height, and BMI.

Table 17: Correlations of FVC with age and its scatter gram

Variable y	FVC
Variable x	age
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.378
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 18: Correlations of FVC with weight and its scatter gram

Variable y	FVC
Variable x	weight
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.468
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 19: Correlations of FVC with height and its scatter gram

Variable y	FVC
Variable x	height
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.553
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 20: Correlations of FVC with BMI and its scatter gram

Variable y	FVC
Variable x	BMI
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.226
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 21: Correlations of FEV₁ with age and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV ₁
Variable x	age
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.368
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 22: Correlations of FEV₁ with weight and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV₁
Variable x	Weight
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.476
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 23: Correlations of FEV₁ with height and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV₁
Variable x	height
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.549
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 24: Correlations of FEV₁ with BMI and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV ₁
Variable x	BMI
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.240
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 25: Correlations of PEFR with age and its scatter gram

Variable y	PEFR
Variable x	age
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.240
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 26: Correlations of PEFR with height and its scatter gram

Variable y	PEFR
Variable x	height
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.324
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 27: Correlations of PEFR with BMI and its scatter gram

Variable y	PEFR
Variable x	BMI
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.324
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 28: Correlations of FEF_{25-75%} with age and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEF _{25-75%}
Variable x	age
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.314
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 29: Correlations of FEF_{25-75%} with weight and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEF _{25-75%}
Variable x	weight
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.439
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 30: Correlations of FEF_{25-75%} with height and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEF _{25-75%}
Variable x	height
Correlation coefficient (r)	0..412
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 31: Correlations of FEF_{25-75%} with BMI and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEF _{25-75%}
Variable x	BMI
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.310
Significance Level (p)	< 0.01

Table 32: correlations of FEV₁/FVC with age and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV ₁ /FVC
Variable x	age
Correlation Coefficient (r)	-0.026
Significance Level (p)	0.644

Table 33: Correlations of FEV₁/FVC with weight and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV ₁ /FVC
Variable x	weight
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.059
Significance Level (p)	0.297

Table 34: Correlations of FEV₁/FVC with height and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV₁/FVC
Variable x	height
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.035
Significance Level (p)	0.238

Table 35: Correlations of FEV₁/FVC with BMI and its scatter gram

Variable y	FEV₁/FVC
Variable x	BMI
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.067
Significance Level (p)	0.541

Table 36: Regression coefficients and constants for Prediction Equations of pulmonary function tests

Parameters	Height (H) (cm)	Weight (W) (kg)	constant	R ²
FVC	0.017	0.005	(-)1.164	0.309
Standard error	0.003	0.004	0.280	
FEV ₁	0.015	0.006	(-)1.061	0.308
Standard error	0.002	0.004	0.254	
PEFR	0.019	0.007	(-)0.874	0.107
Standard error	0.006	0.009	0.622	
FEV _{25-75%}	0.009	0.023	(-)0.469	0.206
Standard error	0.004	0.006	0.420	

Table 37: Regression equations

1.	$FVC = 0.017 \times H + 0.005 \times W - 1.164$
2.	$FEV_1 = 0.015 \times H + 0.006 \times W - 1.061$
3.	$FEV_{25-75\%} = 0.009 \times H + 0.023 \times W - 0.469$
4.	$PEFR = 0.019 \times H + 0.007 \times W - 0.874$

Discussion

Pulmonary function tests play an important role in diagnosis, assessment of severity and response to medications. They are important in children not only for clinical reasons but also due to considerable growth and development of respiratory system which occurs with age. Besides diseases other factors which affect pulmonary functions are genetic, age, sex, height, weight, surface area, race, environment, birth weight, socioeconomic status, duration of breast feeding & history of childhood respiratory tract infections [46,47]. Pulmonary function tests can identify abnormalities of lung volumes, airflow, diffusion, respiratory endurance and respiratory muscle strength. They permit an accurate and reproducible assessment of the respiratory system and allow quantification of the

severity of disease, thereby enabling assessment of the natural history and response to therapy [48].

The purpose of the present study was to derive predictive equations for lung function from healthy children of West Bengal. Reference value describes the level of an index for a group of healthy persons that is the reference population in terms of defining variable, known as reference variable. Commonly used reference variables include ethnic group, age, gender and one or more indices of body size. Thus, the reference values are generated from an equation and the result of an individual subject is obtained by inserting values of his/her features into equation. Number of variables in the reference equation depends on the index. For example, it is more for primary indices such as FEV₁ and FVC to which both body size and age contribute than to their ratio

FEV₁%. In our study after statistical analysis height and weight are used to generate the equation .

The lung function reported from India and other parts of south Asia and most European countries exhibit considerable diversity. Most PFTs were smaller than those calculated by European equations. Most of the studies evaluating PFT in non-European populations have shown greatly reduced lung volumes when compared to European-published reference values [49,50,51,52]. Contributory factors are racial differences, use of a wide variety of equipments and numerous environmental influences including nutrition, climate, terrain and prevalence of diseases. Discrepancies observed among the different sets of prediction equations [41,53-56] with those of the present study may be due to various methodological factors influencing spirometric measurements, for example the equipment and technicians [51,57]. However, the most likely reason for the lower values of PFT derived from prediction equations of the present study may be due to ethnic differences among the study populations. In fact, significant differences in PFTs between race/ethnic groups of Caucasians, African-Americans and Mexican-Americans were demonstrated [52] but, reference equations from the mentioned study [50] were similar to those of other studies [55,58,59]. In fact, African-Americans with similar height for a particular age had lower values of FEV₁ than both Caucasians and Mexican-Americans [59,60] and among Asian-American male and female compared with European-Americans[61]. The PFT values derived from the equations of the present study were even different than those of other studies of our country [56]. In India, several studies were carried out on school children to predict the lung function using anthropometric variables. The studies conducted on children at Chandigarh [26,27], Bombay [28], Delhi [29] and Hyderabad [30] have projected different types of regression equations for lung functions in Indian children. Some of them had used age, height and weight [29], age and height [36], age and body surface area [26,27] or height alone [30] as independent variables for prediction of lung functions. The present study done on Bengali children has used height and weight as independent variables for the prediction equations of FVC, FEV₁, FEV_{25-75%} and PEFr.

Statistical analysis was carried out using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) 16.0 and, Analysis was carried out separately in boys and girls. In the present study, the dependent variables were FVC, FEV₁, PEFr and FEV_{25-75%}. Pearson's correlation analysis was carried out to identify the predictor variables. Prediction equations were developed using the multiple linear regression procedure. Linear and nonlinear models were developed and the former was selected based on

criteria of simplicity and ease of clinical application, high predictive capability (R²) and yield of smallest residuals. The independent variables were entered in the sequence of height, age and weight. Models were constructed including one (height), two (height and age) and three predictor variables (height, age and weight) and R², adjusted R² and R² change on entering each predictor variable were calculated for each model. If the R² change at each step was significant and there was a substantial improvement in the predictive ability, the model was accepted. If not, the model at the previous step was accepted. Standard errors of the estimate (SEE) were calculated and analysis of variance was carried out for each model to evaluate the significance of the regression equations. Estimates of regression coefficients were obtained and their significance was determined by student's 't' test.

We calculated lung function reference values for FVC, FEV₁, FEF_{25%-75%}, and PEFr in relation to age, height, BMI and weight for normal and healthy school children aged 6 to 12 years in Howrah district of West Bengal. Our results are from a relatively broad population sample comprising of 310 children of which 138 are boys and 172 are girls that were selected using strict disease exclusion criteria recommended by the ATS. [16,17] Since the school children examined, represented both the rural and urban population of varied socioeconomic strata of Howrah district of West Bengal, the corresponding confounding factors of race, ethnicity, rural and urban are excluded. In addition, all the flow volume curves obtained were computer-validated in real time. The best-fit model generated by stepwise multiple regression was obtained following logarithmic transformation of the spirometric results and using the following predictors → height, weight, age and BMI. The percentage distribution of the boys and girls of the representative population according to the age distribution are shown in the table 1. The pulmonary function distribution in boys and girls for the whole sample is shown in table 12 representing the mean with standard deviation, median and the 25th, 50th and 75th percentiles showing a normal distribution.

In the present study, FVC, FEV₁, FEF_{25-75%} and PEFr increases with increased age in both sexes while, FEV₁/FVC % did not show any remarkable change but remained almost constant in all age groups. Also, it is seen that the values were higher in boys in all age groups except in the 12 years age category where the values of both were almost the same as shown in table 2 and 3.

Also it was seen that the lung function parameters except FEV₁/FVC increased with increased weight of the children except those belonging to the weight category >45 kg in girls where it showed a slight decrease than the previous categories as shown in table 4 and 5. As for the boys whose values were higher

than the girls, as was previously seen, the lung function parameters except FEV_1/FVC increased with increased weight except those belonging to weight category >35 kg as shown in table 5.

Similarly, all lung function parameters excepting FEV_1/FVC increases with increased height for both sexes with values of boys greater than that of girls as shown in table 6 and 7.

Same results were obtained with BMI for both sexes with values of boys greater than that of girls as shown in table 8 and 9.

Bhattacharya and Banerjee in Jaipur also observed that vital capacity increases with increase in age in both the sexes and they also found that females have lower vital capacities than males [62]. Chowgule et al in Bombay also found that boys have higher values of FVC than girls [28]. Sharma et al in Delhi also observed that FVC values were significantly ($p<0.05$) greater for boys than girls [29]. Vijayan et al found that in south Indian children, the mean FVC values were 2.43 ± 0.07 liter in boys and 1.86 ± 0.05 liter in girls, which was significantly high in boys [32]. The mean values of FVC in our study were 1.256 ± 0.3313 liter for boys and 1.165 ± 0.40006 liter for girls and values were significantly higher in boys (table 13 and table 14). Though the mean values of FVC of boys aged 10-12 years in our study were slightly different than those obtained by Sharma et al, Raju et al [29,30] and also others as mentioned above. This could be explained by a multitude of factors that affect FVC apart from anthropometry to environment, socioeconomic factors and race which need further evaluation. FVC, FEV_1 , and $FEF_{25-75\%}$ were found higher for boys as compared to girls. But the difference was statistically highly significant ($p<0.01$) for FVC, FEV_1 , $FEF_{25-75\%}$ and PEF (table 10 and table 11). We also correlated the mean values of FEV_1 in different age groups in both males and females of 10-12 years of age and observed that the correlation of FEV_1 increases with increase in age, weight, height, BSA and BMI as shown in (table 2 to 9). The correlation of FEV_1 with these variables was statistically significant ($p<0.01$). This was similar to the observations made earlier by Sharma et al, Raju et al, Vijayan et al. and Chowgule et al., in various parts of India [28,29,30,32]. The mean values of FEV_1 were similar to the mean values obtained by Sharma et al and Raju et al. in boys of same age. We also observed that FEV_1 increases with increase in BMI as shown in table 8 and 9 as described previously. The increase was more marked till a BMI of $23.0-26.99$ kg/m^2 in both males and in females. The correlation coefficients for FEV_1 with BMI were 0.173 for males and 0.313 for females (table 10 and 11). Correlation coefficients for FVC, FEV_1 , FEV_1

$/FVC\%$ and $FEF_{25-75\%}$ with age, weight, height and BMI for both males and females are shown which is reflecting a good correlation. The correlation was found to be statistically highly significant ($p<0.01$) for all the variables.

From table 2-9, it was also analyzed that there is no relationship of $FEV_1/FVC\%$ with age, weight, height and BMI in children of 10-12 years of age in both the sexes. We also computed correlation coefficients of $FEV_1/FVC\%$ with age and anthropometric measurements ($p>0.05$). Correlation coefficient values of $FEV_1/FVC\%$ with age (0.116-males, 0.130-females), weight (0.027-males, -0.083-females), height (-0.050-males, -0.025-females), and BMI (0.030-males, -0.103 females) were observed (table 10 and 11). Vijayan et al. did not find significant correlation of $FEV_1/FVC\%$ with age, height and weight [32]. Sharma et al observed that $FEV_1/FVC\%$ was more than 80% in age and sex categories and the difference being insignificant between the two sexes [29]. The mean values of $FEV_1/FVC\%$ for boys in our study were lower than the mean values reported by Raju et al for all age groups [30].

In our study, Forced expiratory flow ($FEF_{25-75\%}$) showed increase with increase in age, weight, height and BMI in both sexes (table 2-9). The correlation of $FEF_{25-75\%}$ was significant ($p<0.01$) with all anthropometric measures. Vijayan et al. found correlation between $FEF_{25-75\%}$ and age, weight and height to be significant ($p<0.01$) [32]. Coefficient of correlation was highest with height and was higher in boys than girls. In both boys and girls (table 10 and 11), we found that $FEF_{25-75\%}$ was significantly correlated with age and height. Sharma et al also observed significant ($p<0.001$) increase in $FEF_{25-75\%}$ with age and height in both sexes [29].

The present study intended to derive the prediction formula for estimation of the expected values of lung function in children between 6-12 years based on height, weight, age and sex. In the present study as there was no observed variation in lung function tests with sex as was demonstrated by independent sample 't' test as $p>0.05$, prediction formula was not separately formulated for both boys and girls, but a common regression equation were formulated for the lung function parameters for the whole cohort using multiple regression analysis as described above using height and weight as two independent variables. These equations derived can be used to predict the lung function of children from Eastern India. Pulmonary function test depends on many factors; regional variation is one of them. No study has been conducted in this region of India, so the present study was done to know the baseline

pulmonary function test in the healthy school children of Howrah district of West Bengal in East India. The limitation of the study was more children could have been included in each subgroup. In the present study these equations were obtained for very young children (aged 6-12 years). Measurement of PFT values in very young children are very difficult

because of cooperation of such young children for these measurements. However, in the present study, major efforts have been done to obtain the most accurate PFT values in the studied population. The PFT measurements were done by myself after full training. The children were fully trained before PFT measurement and were encouraged to do their best during performance.

Summary and Conclusion

We found linear positive correlation of FVC, FEV₁, and FEF_{25-75%} and PEF with age, height, weight and BMI for both boys and girls. There were some differences in pulmonary function between the values obtained in our study and the studies done earlier on Indian children. This could possibly be due to multiple factors; ethnic background, environmental, body build, socioeconomic status, and pollution. Lung function values in boys were found to be significantly higher as compared to girls. Height is the most important and reliable single independent variable.

The prediction equations derived from the present study are suitable for children of 6-12 years of age group. Discrepancies observed among the different sets of prediction equations (both European [31,40,52-56] and Indian [30,36,41-43]) with those of the present study are small but significant and may be due to various reasons. Apart from race and ethnicity [41,49,51,52], age differences between study populations are considerable. Present study included children of 6-12 years age group; while others [32,33,34] had an extended adolescent study group, who were analysed at an early stage of puberty. It is well known that pubertal growth influences lung function [64] and that spirometric prediction equations developed for children and adolescents should not be extrapolated to other age groups [16,17]. Also sample size [33] is another factor affecting precision of the prediction equations.

Measurement of lung function is an integral part of modern management of both restrictive and obstructive lung disease. A wider application of this instrument, both by the doctor and patient, will help to improve the quality of life in patients suffering from asthma and other pulmonary disease. The present study will definitely help to interpret the observed lung function values in local children of Eastern India.

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